

**SPEECH COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT IN FOREIGN STUDENTS
AT CLASSES ON UKRAINIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE
(PREPARATION DEPARTMENT)**

Today, the idea of a practical orientation of the academic subject “Ukrainian as a foreign language” is increasingly being established in the activities of the preparatory departments. While the speech competence development is a complex concept and covers the system of speech skills, which formation should be carried out at the elementary level (A1-A2), in accordance with the requirements of the educational program.

The aim of learning Ukrainian as a foreign language at the elementary level is “primarily to form foreign students' ability to make sentences within the limits of conversational topics available to them” [2].

The analysis of the literature on the outlined issue [3; 4; 5] proved that the topic of our research is an integral part of the general problem “Interrelated study of theoretical knowledge of Ukrainian and the formation of practical speaking skills in foreigners”, which solution contributes to the implementation of an activity approach to teaching Ukrainian as a foreign language, according to the requirements of the State Standards of Ukraine [1; 2].

As a part of our research, a small experiment was conducted with a group of foreign students. The experiment involved 17 students from one group of the preparatory department from different countries of the world, aged from 19 to 25 years. The initial level of the participants was the same: students did not speak Ukrainian, did not know how to read and write, did not understand anything. In the first lesson, students used only sign language to understand what the teacher wanted from them. The teacher did not teach only the grammar of Ukrainian, but began by teaching the communicative component through grammatical categories. After 3 weeks of intensive study (15 classes per week), the following results were obtained:

1. The students could state how was their day and what they did during the week in Ukrainian. They started writing their own texts 2 weeks after the beginning of the classes.

2. The students could tell about themselves: what are their names, how old are they, what do they like to do, what food do they like.

3. The students could write dictations in the form of phrases and simple sentences. The maximum number of errors was 5.5 errors per 30 words. That is, students' phonemic hearing was developed quite well.

4. The students studied verb conjugation, gender and number of adjectives and nouns, present and future tenses; formation of accusative and prepositional cases.

5. The students read unfamiliar texts at a speed of 25–30 words per minute.

6. The students started the texts' retelling, but faced the following problems: a) a small amount of vocabulary that is slowly replenished: the students use only those words that they learn in the classes with the teacher. It was a standard set of lexical units: nouns – animals, fruits, vegetables, food, clothes, furniture, dishes, etc., adjectives – colors, emotions, active voice of the most used verbs. Therefore, increasing the vocabulary is one of the priority areas of education. b) speech competence development – these were only answers to questions about self-presentation, hobbies, interests, and preferences.

Because of this communicative approach to learning Ukrainian as a foreign language, within three weeks, foreign students went from zero language proficiency to the ability to speak, write, read and think in Ukrainian at the elementary level. During 45 classes, the teachers used faceted teaching (phonetics, vocabulary, grammar, writing, conversational practice) with a focus on communication, using not only textbooks, but also ICT tools, etc., which is quite relevant during distance learning. The results of the experiment make it possible to confirm that such a regular and planned approach to learning Ukrainian as a foreign language gives a positive result and in the long term will contribute to the mastery of Ukrainian language by foreign students at a sufficient level.

References

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